

May 1, 2025

JOURNAL OF
INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE
NETWORKS

SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

www.bestjournalup.com

Conference directions:

1. Scientific technologies
2. Economy
3. Biotechnology
4. Mathematical analysis
5. Technical sciences
6. Pedagogy
7. Psychology
8. Philosophy
9. History
10. Informatics

INDEXING

zenodo

OpenAIRE | EXPLORE

UDC: 001.891

International scientific and practical conference. International scientific and Applied Research. 10.05.2025.

In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

© *International scientific and practical conference. 2025.*

© Journal of International science networks. 2025.

BIOTEXNOLOGIYANING TIBBIYOTDAGI O‘RNI

Bozorboyeva Madina Zokirjon qizi
Sobirova Muqaddas Batirovna

O‘zbekiston Milliy universiteti Jizzax filiali Biotexnologiya kafedrası
email: bozorboyevamadina3@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tezisda biotexnologiyaning tibbiyot sohasidagi o‘rni va ahamiyati ko‘rib chiqilgan. Zamonaviy tibbiyotda biotexnologiya diagnostika, dori-darmon ishlab chiqarish, regenerativ tibbiyot va gen terapiyasi kabi yo‘nalishlarda muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Biotexnologik usullar yordamida turli kasalliklarni erta aniqlash, individual davolash usullarini ishlab chiqish va organizmning tabiiy regeneratsiya jarayonlarini qo‘llab-quvvatlash imkoniyatlari kengaymoqda. Shuningdek, biofarmatsevtika va rekombinant DNK texnologiyalari orqali samarali dori vositalari ishlab chiqilayotgani ta‘kidlangan. Tezida biotexnologiyaning tibbiyotdagi istiqbollari va innovatsion yondashuvlar ham muhokama qilingan.

Kalit so‘zlar: Biotexnologiya, gen terapiyasi, regenerativ tibbiyot, biofarmatsevtika, diagnostika, rekombinant DNK, hisoblash kimyosi, bioinformatika, veterinariya, vaksinalar.

Kirish: Bugungi kunda biotexnologiya tibbiyot sohasida tub burilish yasamoqda. An‘anaviy davolash usullaridan farqli ravishda, biotexnologiya gen terapiyasi, regenerativ tibbiyot, diagnostika va biofarmatsevtika kabi yo‘nalishlarda inqilobiy yutuqlarga erishmoqda. Ushbu fan DNK muhandisligi, rekombinant oqsillar va hujayra texnologiyalaridan foydalanib, kasalliklarni erta aniqlash, samarali davolash va oldini olish imkoniyatlarini kengaytirmoqda. Shu sababli, biotexnologiyaning tibbiyotdagi roli ortib bormoqda va u kelajakda sog‘liqni saqlash tizimini yanada rivojlantirishda muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi [1].

So‘nggi yillarda, ayniqsa, tibbiyot va sog‘liqni saqlash sohalarida biotexnologiya mahsulotlarining keskin o‘shishini kuzatmoqdamiz. Ayniqsa, penitsillin (antibiotik), rekombinant insulin va hujayra asosidagi terapiyaning kashf etilishi tibbiy diagnostika va davolash usullarida inqilob sodir etdi. Biotexnologiya – bu muhandislik vositalari yordamida foydali terapevtik mahsulotlarni ishlab chiqish uchun tirik organizmlardan foydalanadigan amaliy biologiya sohasi. Biotexnologiyaning to‘rtta asosiy sanoat yo‘nalishlari mavjud: sog‘liqni saqlash (tibbiyot), ekinlarni yetishtirish va qishloq xo‘jaligi, ekinlarning oziq-ovqat bo‘lmagan (sanoat) sohada qo‘llanilishi hamda boshqa mahsulotlar (masalan, biologik parchalanadigan plastmassa, o‘simlik moyi, bioyoqilg‘i) va ekologik foydalanish. Shu yo‘nalishlar orasida, biotexnologiyaning tibbiy jihatlari keng miqyosda sog‘liqni saqlash mahsulotlari va diagnostika vositalarini ishlab chiqishda qo‘llanilmoqda. Tibbiyotda zamonaviy biotexnologiya dori vositalari ishlab chiqarish, farmakogenomika, gen terapiyasi va genetik testlash kabi sohalarda

istiqbolli qo'llanilish imkoniyatiga ega. Tibbiy biotexnologiya sohasi doimiy ravishda yangi kashfiyotlar va mahsulotlar bilan rivojlanib bormoqda [2].

So'nggi o'n yilliklarda ildiz hujayralar texnologiyasi tibbiy biotexnologiyada inqilobiy o'zgarishlarga sabab bo'ldi. Bu hujayralarning cheksiz o'z-o'zini yangilash va inson tanasining barcha hujayralari hamda to'qimalarini hosil qilish qobiliyati tibbiyotda katta imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda. Ko'plab ilmiy izlanishlar shikastlangan hujayralar yoki to'qimalarni tiklash yoki almashtirish maqsadida zamonaviy ildiz hujayra terapiyalarini ishlab chiqishga yo'naltirilgan bo'lib, bu texnologiya halokatli kasalliklarga qarshi samarali davolash usullarini yaratish umidini uyg'otmoqda. Shubhasiz, bu innovatsion texnologiya kelajakda ildiz hujayralarga asoslangan mahsulot va xizmatlarning istiqboliga sarmoya kiritishga ishonch uyg'otadi. Ushbu tezesda ildiz hujayralari, embrion va induktsiyalangan pluripotent ildiz hujayralarining biotexnologiyadagi qo'llanilishi va ularning biznes imkoniyatlari bayon etiladi. Shunga qaramay, ildiz hujayralarning tibbiyotga qo'shgan hissasi beqiyos bo'lsa-da, bir qator to'siqlar mavjud: etik va huquqiy muammolar, ildiz hujayra ajdodlarining funksional yetilishi, qat'iy ishlab chiqarish standartlari, immunitet tizimining rad etishi va o'simalarning shakllanish xavfi. Shuningdek, mikrofluidika texnologiyasi, "idish ichida organ" va 3D biochop etish usullari bo'yicha muhim ilmiy tadqiqotlar e'lon qilindi. Ushbu yondashuvlar inson pluripotent ildiz hujayralariga asoslangan sog'lom va kasallik modellarini yaratish orqali kasallik mexanizmlarini aniqlash, dori vositalarini kashf qilish va toksikologik tadqiqotlarni rivojlantirishda muvaffaqiyatli qo'llanilmoqda. Yangi maqsadlar sonining ortib borishi sababli, hisoblash kimyosi va bioinformatika yordamisiz tajribalarda sinovdan o'tkazilishi kerak bo'lgan molekulalar sonini qisqartirish mumkin emas. So'nggi yillarda butun dunyo bo'ylab bioinformatika va mashinaviy o'rganish bilan shug'ullanuvchi kompaniyalar va startaplar sonining keskin o'sishi kuzatilmoqda [3]. Bundan tashqari, hozirgi kunda biotexnologik yondashuvlar veterinariya tibbiyotida ham keng qo'llanilmoqda va ildiz hujayralarga asoslangan biotexnologiya inson terapevtikasida yangi davrni ochmoqda.

Tibbiy biotexnologiya sohasi jadal rivojlanmoqda va bu kasalliklarning oldini olish, diagnostika qilish hamda davolash uchun bir qator innovatsion texnikalar ishlab chiqilishiga olib kelmoqda. Polimeraza zanjirli reaksiya, gen sekvenirlash, floresan in situ gibridizatsiya, mikrochip texnologiyasi, hujayra madaniyati, interferensial RNK yordamida gen susaytirish va genomni tahrirlash kabi yangi metodologiyalar sog'liqni saqlash fanining rivojlanishiga sezilarli hissa qo'shmoqda. Ushbu yondashuvlar inson genomining to'liq ketma-ketligini aniqlash, regenerativ tibbiyotda ildiz hujayralardan foydalanish, to'qima muhandisligi, antibiotiklar ishlab chiqish va terapiya uchun monoklonal antitanachalar yaratish kabi yutuqlarga yo'l ochdi [4].

Xulosa: Biotexnologiya tibbiyot sohasida inqilobiy o'zgarishlar qilishga xizmat qilayotgan muhim yo'nalishlardan biridir. U biologik jarayonlar va organizmlardan foydalangan holda innovatsion dori vositalari, vaksinalar, diagnostika tizimlari hamda regenerativ tibbiyot texnologiyalarini yaratishda muhim

rol o'ynaydi. Gen muhandisligi va hujayra terapiyasi yordamida irsiy kasalliklarni davolash, biotexnologik vaksinalar orqali yuqumli kasalliklarning oldini olish, biopolimer va regenerativ tibbiyot usullari bilan jarrohlik amaliyotlarining samaradorligini oshirish mumkin. Shuningdek, biotexnologiya individual tibbiyotga yo'l ochib, har bir bemorga moslashtirilgan davo usullarini ishlab chiqishga imkon beradi. Kelajakda biotexnologiyaning rivojlanishi tibbiyotda yanada samarali va ekologik xavfsiz davolash usullarini yaratishga xizmat qiladi. Shuning uchun ushbu fan yo'nalishi sog'liqni saqlash tizimida muhim o'rin tutadi va insoniyatning uzoq umr ko'rishi hamda turli kasalliklarga chalinish xavfini kamaytirishda asosiy omillardan biri bo'lib qoladi.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar ro'yxati:

1. Gonnella J. S., Hojat M. Biotechnology and ethics in medical education of the new millennium: physician roles and responsibilities //Medical Teacher. – 2001. – T. 23. – №. 4. – C. 371-377.
2. Khan F. A. Biotechnology in medical sciences. – CRC Press, 2014.
3. Saxena, Ajit Kumar, Divya Singh, and Jyoti Gupta. "Role of stem cell research in therapeutic purpose--a hope for new horizon in medical biotechnology." *Journal of experimental therapeutics & oncology* 8.3 (2010).
4. Pham, Phuc V. "Medical biotechnology: techniques and applications." *Omics technologies and bio-engineering*. Academic Press, 2018. 449-469.